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STUDY REPORT

Domestic Violence: The Male Struggle to Survive and Mental health.

VOICE OF VOICELESS

Prepared By:

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This survey and study report is based on Valid Statistics from National Crime Bureau (NCRB), reference from other study reports, Media coverage or testimonials from the victims, and not collected as Women organizations collect from Fake statistics or cooked up sob stories which have no valid backing.

Summary: The term "Domestic Violence/Abuse" covers a broad range of violent acts committed by one member of a family or household against another. It often refers to the mistreatment of a child or spouse and can include not only physical harm, but also threats and verbal, psychological, and sexual abuse. Most of the time, domestic violence against men only gets any attention when a Celebrity/Politician or highly reputed person is the victim of some kind of noteworthy physical harm, rest perceived as isolated incidents and much of the public and private speculation presumes the man did something to deserve it.

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The exact numbers on domestic violence on men overall is difficult to assess as majority cases go unreported, but it's even tougher to figure out just how many men are suffering abuse. A big part of the reason is traditional gender roles in society and the stigma of the perceived weakness of any man who admits to falling victim to a woman.

Key Findings: Majority men are ashamed to come forward to report domestic violence/abuse on them by their wives, as there are no laws or Authority to report, reporting their abuse will be an Invitation to bigger trouble and charged with false cases like 498A IPC / PWDVA 2005 on them, that make's men to suffer in silence.

Methodology: Information for this report was sourced from various secondary sources, all listed in the Reference List. Data from NCRB and various News publications and testimonies, Survey statistics of victims of Domestic violence also proved valuable. This report is not a comprehensive review of the available literature but provides a broad overview of the topic. It is an effort to highlight the plight of Men who are neglected by World Organizations and Government bodies. Even none of the survey data study Institutes or Media is not ready to Publish Domestic Violence/Abuse on Men or their Mental health.

Introduction: MyNation analysis of statistics on Domestic Violence shows the number of men attacked/abused/harassed/killed by wives and girlfriends is much higher than ever thought. Its report, Domestic Violence: The Male struggle to survive, states: "Domestic Violence is often assumed as women as victim and men as perpetrator/abuser, but the evidence collected by MyNation demonstrates that this is a false predomination, promoted by feminists and women organizations."

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MyNation Hope Foundation with a presence on the internet for over 15 years and having more than 10,000 families registered with them that include men, women and old aged parents. The study conducted between January 2018 and March 2020 by Social workers, Researchers, Doctors, IT Engineers, Bankers and MyNation. From all over India, 90% of the respondents and 10% NRIs had suffered Domestic Violence more than once in their lives. The study covered men of Indian origin from various socio-economic groups but most of the respondents, according to the researchers, come from the upper middle class and middle class.

About three in five of Domestic Violence instances are on men, contradicting the widespread impression that it is almost always women who are left battered and bruised. About 3000 men aged between 25-55 years, selected through random sampling are interviewed using a schedule adapted from the WHO multi-country study on Men's Health and Domestic Violence.

The study looked at all four aspects of Domestic Violence, Emotional, Physical, Sexual and Economical. Emotional violence is found to be the most common with 43.2% respondents mentioning they had faced it atleast once, followed by Physical (26.8%), then by Sexual (19.8%) and Economical violence (10.2%).

“The violence is found to be more on men. This clearly indicates lack of awareness and support among masses regarding emotional violence on men. The men, who are contributors to the society in the name of father, son, brother, husband, entrepreneur, taxpayer, army soldier and more are often subjected to emotional violence which is not lesser than any heinous crime.” says **Dr. Bharat Bhushan**.

“An interesting finding is that the probability of violence increased significantly with the duration of marriage particularly if it was more than five years old” says one of the researchers. "So much for the law to promote domestic violence against Indian men and wonder no NGO or Social organizations have done any research, no one demanded the data of Crime against men by women and crime against

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women by another women. Indian government is mostly interested to promote 'Beti Bachao' by funding more than INR 25,000 crore yearly but none to men and his families. Indian Gender Biased Laws have major impact on failure of marital relationship and are affecting the normal growth of children involved. Very soon the Indian Civilized Institution of marriage system will be dwindled and in coming years there will be many children alienated from father." he said.

Objective of the Study:

Men assaulted by their partners are often ignored by police. Cases are not filed. Mostly the women attackers go scot free. Men have far fewer shelter homes to flee to. Compared to women, men don't have any protection laws from domestic abuse.

"National Commission for Women is taking very good care of the desires of unscrupulous wives/daughters-in-laws. Wives can falsely accuse their husband and in-laws, then blackmail them for money. Wives can extort money by threatening their husband of filing a false case. Wives can kick their husband and in-laws from the marital house under domestic violence laws. Wives can have extramarital affairs proudly with anybody even when the husband and in-laws are fully aware of it. In short, it is simply great to be born as a woman in India. Whatever she does, she will always be considered a victim. Surely, these women will be extremely thankful to NCW for legalizing their adultery. What is illegal is now legal.

Adultery is not illegal in India now, so What more do the women want now?" asks **Dr. Vikas Singh Rawat.**

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According to the research, 53 per cent of Indian wives admitted to having had an intimate relationship outside their marriage (Ref:<https://supari.org/40-percent>). she can have sex in front of her husband at his home, but he cannot do anything legally as Section 497 IPC scrapped by Indian judiciary to promote and empower women.

Today, legally any woman can file a case on man and all her allegations are assumed “possible” as they stayed under one roof and closed walls. These baseless allegations can be shattered through proper investigation, but India has Investigation Officers and Protection Officers who do not even know the basics of complaint verification process. There are scenarios, where the bride has comeback after a year of eloping with someone, but the Groom's family had spent that one year in jail on charges of bride’s murder. Corruption also plays a major role in the misuse of these gender biased laws.

The latest health statistics paint a grim picture of India’s mental health of men revealing that one person commits suicide every four minutes. The National Health Profile 2018 raises alarm over the increasing numbers of suicide deaths—a whopping 1,33,623 in a year.

This translates into 366 suicide deaths every day and 15 an hour.

The data also show increasing vulnerability of Indian men vis-à-vis women.

Nearly 70 per cent of all suicide deaths in India involve males. Of the 1,33,623 people who killed themselves, 68.49 per cent (91,528) were men as against 42,088 women.

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The number of suicides by men has risen from 66,032 in 2000 and 80,544 in 2008 to 91,528 currently. The number of male deaths from suicides is nearly double than that of females.

According to the latest data, the highest suicide burden is in Maharashtra (16,970 deaths), followed by Tamil Nadu (15,777) and Bengal (14,602).

Health data also reveal that suicides are the highest in the productive age group of 30 to 45. Trends call for massive shift in government policy to address the rising burden of mental health disorders, an emerging challenge under the larger non-communicable disease bracket.

WHO's Global Disease Burden released last month also underlined the need for member nations to contain suicide deaths by tweaking policy. WHO asked all member states to ensure employers factor in mental health when crafting recruitment policies? (Source: <https://www.tribuneindia.com/news/archive/nation/-one-indian-commits-suicide-every-4-minutes-men-more-vulnerable-609058>)

Data from the Survey show that men made up about 45% of Domestic Violence victims each year between 2018-19 and last year for which figures are unavailable. In 2016-17 men made up 43.4% of all those who had suffered partner abuse in the previous year, which rose to 45.5% in 2017-18.

The 2018-19 survey shows one in three men had experienced domestic abuse since the age of 16. As per MyNation, men are often treated as "second-class victims" and that many police forces and councils do not take them seriously. "Male victims are almost invisible to the authorities such as the police, who rarely can be prevailed upon to take the man's side," said **Aman Kumar**, a Banker by profession. "Their plight is largely overlooked by the media, in official reports and in government policy, for example Women organization like WCD/NCW are ministry for women with around 25,000 crore yearly funding but none for Men,

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even though most of the taxpayers are Men” says **Vikrant Banode** an IT Professional.

The official figures underestimate the true number of male victims, **Amit Nishania** a Finance professional said. "Culturally it's difficult for men to bring these incidents to the attention of the authorities. Men are reluctant to say that they have been abused by women, because it's considered as unmanly and weak."

"Both men and women can be victims and we know that men feel immense pressure to keep up the pretense that everything is OK, Domestic abuse against a man is just as abhorrent as when a woman is treated as the victim always." said **Ramesh Thatiseti** an NRI, ""

No provisions of refuge or Legal Aid for men.

“Male victims are almost invisible to the authorities and Government” says **Rudolph Dsouza** of MyNation, an Initiative, a helpline for Male victims, He added "It's a scandal that even in 2020 all Domestic Violence victims are still not being treated equally. Men are not only abused with Emotional, Physical, Sexual, and Economic violence, but also with LEGAL TERRORISM. We reject the gendered analysis that so many in the Domestic Violence establishment still pursue, that is the primary focus should be female victims only. Each victim should be seen as an individual and helped accordingly."

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Shocking! Indian wives rank third in beating their husbands:

We often hear stories of husbands thrash their wife for various reasons, but the other side of the story is husbands too are persecuted in large numbers. So much so that Indian women are ranked third in the world for abusing or beating their husbands. A study conducted by the UN in a couple of years ago (2016) has revealed shocking statistics of domestic violence on husbands. These figures indicate that domestic violence is the most frequent in Egypt, while UK stood second followed by India.

The survey states that wives used items like belts, shoes, utensils etc. to beat their husbands. It was also trending on twitter at that time.

Users commented that when a woman becomes a victim then the whole world stands by her, but the society turns a blind eye when a man is found to be on the receiving end. Husbands who suffer such abuse find no other way to defend them and knock the doors of law to save themselves from abuse and assault.(Source : <https://www.orissapost.com/shocking-indian-wives-rank-third-in-beating-their-husbands>)

False Propaganda of Women Organizations.

As these Women ministry claim "Many women suffering abuse want to go to their mother's house, but during the lockdown, they can only be sent to state-run shelter homes, where the risk of overcrowding and poor hygiene runs high."

When WCD/NCW has 25,000 crores of yearly funding why these shelter homes are unhygienic? ask **Neeraj Pattath** a MyNation members.

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"For the first week, the number of calls we get fell, and we believe this is because women were basically locked in with their abusers," Swetha Shankar, director of client services at the Women organization.

India's Domestic Violence Act gives the woman a right to shelter. Let her stay home in her house, with her kids, and let the man be sent to a shelter home if he is going to abuse the woman in the middle of a pandemic. "Why should a woman escaping abuse in the middle of a lockdown be sent to a shelter home where she risks catching coronavirus?" Vrinda Grover, a leading feminist lawyer.

As earlier said by these women organizations, they are not getting any calls, then how they know these women are harassed or abused. Either they should know magic or telepathy, stated one of the survey participant.

WCD/NCW opposes any sort of law for men against women or setup Ministry, as they have strong feminist lobby, they opposed dilution and punishment for filing false cases of 498a/DV Act too. so without giving any option for men to complain or disclose about being abused by their wives, they just want to showcase that only women are harassed by men and portray them as villains and only women are the real victims.(Source:<https://thewire.in/gender/section-498a-domestic-abuse-ncw>)

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HOW WOMEN HARASS:

Emotional, Physical, Sexual and Economical abuse on men: Men are abused by women, it happens, and it matters.

So, what is abuse? A pattern of controlling behavior, Abuse in intimate relationships is a pattern of behavior where one partner dominates, belittles or humiliates the other over months and years.

Abuse of men by their partners happens when the partner uses emotional, physical, sexual or intimidation tactics. She does it to control the man, get her own way and prevent him from leaving the relationship. The abused man is always adapting his behavior to do what his partner wants, in the hopes of preventing further abuse.

The primary motive for abuse is to establish and maintain power and control over a partner. The abused partner may resist the attempts to control him. In turn, the abusive woman takes additional steps to regain control over her partner.

Abuse in intimate relationships is not typically an isolated incident. Abuse happens overtime. Typically, if abuse is allowed to continue, it becomes more frequent and more severe.

Abuse is always a choice. Whatever people's background or experience, they must take responsibility for their actions. No one has the right to abuse someone else, and no one deserves abuse.

CONTROL TACTICS: Four kinds of abuse

Often when people think about abuse, they think of emotional abuse, physical abuse or sexual abuse. Abuse may also include intimidation tactics.

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EMOTIONAL ABUSE:

Emotional abuse happen without other abuse tactics involved, emotional abuse is almost always present. Some men say it is harder to deal with emotional abuse than physical abuse. Emotional abuse includes:

- ✓ Putdowns: Insults or humiliates her partner at home or in public
- ✓ Blames him
- ✓ Lies to him
- ✓ Insult/abuse husband Family members.
- ✓ Curse/Grumble/Insult husband.
- ✓ Give threat of False 498a/DV criminal cases
- ✓ Give threat to alienate children from him.
- ✓ Embarrass in front of friends/Family members.
- ✓ Shaming
- ✓ Name calling, specially to mother-in-law
- ✓ Isolating her partner and restricting his freedom
- ✓ Controls her partner's social interaction
- ✓ Isolates him from friends and family
- ✓ Treats him like a servant
- ✓ Monitors his phone calls
- ✓ Restricts his ability to get around
- ✓ Controls access to information or participation in organizations and groups.
- ✓ Insults
- ✓ Accusations on character and conduct etc.
- ✓ Preventing you or a child in your custody from attending school, college or any other educational institution
- ✓ Preventing you from taking up a job, forcing you to leave your job
- ✓ Preventing you or a child in your custody from leaving the house
- ✓ Preventing you from meeting any person in the normal course of events
- ✓ Forcing you to get married when you don't want to marry
- ✓ Preventing you from marrying a person of your own choice

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- ✓ Forcing you to marry a particular person of his/their own choice
- ✓ Threaten to commit suicide
- ✓ Any other verbal or emotional abuse

SPIRITUAL ABUSE:

- ✓ Ridicules or insults her partner's spiritual beliefs
- ✓ Makes it difficult for the partner to be with others in his spiritual community

Emotional violence has become more common against men and openly neglected as there is no law to support men who are in abusive relationships and are victims of domestic violence. This kind of Emotional violence is more common in Indian family which is often neglected by court of law, police authority and society as a whole.

PHYSICAL ABUSE:

This includes any activity that can cause physical pain or injury.

In an intimate relationship, physical abuse happens when the abusive person:

- ✓ Shoves, slaps, hits, kicks or bites
- ✓ Throws/drop things on him
- ✓ Uses a weapon
- ✓ Intentionally interferes with basic daily requirements for food, shelter, medicine and sleep
- ✓ Beating
- ✓ Throw things/hot water/hot oil/Acid
- ✓ Mix life threatening things or slow poison in eatables.
- ✓ Beating, slapping, hitting, biting, kicking, punching, pushing, shoving or causing bodily pain or injury in any other manner.

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SEXUAL ABUSE:

- ✓ Uses force or pressure to get her partner to have sex in a way he does not want
- ✓ Ridicules or criticizes his performance
- ✓ Withholds affection and sex to punish him for violating her rules
- ✓ Withhold sex without reason.
- ✓ Abuse for weaker sexual drive or size.
- ✓ Accuse of having Affair. (Even some men reported, that abusing and accusing to having sex with mother)
- ✓ Doubting of relation with neighbour/co-worker
- ✓ Forced sexual intercourse
- ✓ Forces to look at pornography or any other obscene pictures or material
- ✓ Any act of sexual nature to abuse, humiliate or degrade you, or which is otherwise volatile of dignity or any other unwelcome conduct of sexual nature

ECONOMICAL ABUSE:

- ✓ Controlling finances
- ✓ Withholds financial information from her partner
- ✓ Steals money from him
- ✓ Makes financial decisions that affect him without asking or telling him
- ✓ Desert without any grounds and claim Maintenance
- ✓ File False case of Domestic violence also take children with her and claim alimony
- ✓ File False case of Dowry (IPC 498A) and force man to settle out of court with huge sum of money and property
- ✓ On False Ground of Domestic violence occupy husband home making him homeless.
- ✓ Not providing you money for maintaining you or your children
- ✓ Not providing food, clothes, medicines etc for you or your children
- ✓ Stopping you from carrying on your employment or disturbing you

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in carrying on your employment

- ✓ Not allowing you to take up an employment or taking away your income from your salary, wages etc
- ✓ Forcing you out of the house you live in
- ✓ Stopping you from accessing or using any part of the house
- ✓ Not allowing use of clothes, articles or things of general household use
- ✓ Not paying rent if staying in a rented accommodation.

Other than Economic Terrorism, Women use Legal terrorism to make money, most of the dowry cases (IPC 498A) and DV Act 2005 filed, man under pressure succumb to her demand and settle out with huge amount of money. Any time women can walk out taking children and file any False case on husband, no proof or evidence needed. On the basis of these Fake DV cases judge order maintenance of huge amount, there are many such judgments, even Men are unemployed still court order Alimony/Maintenance. In an exceptional order, the Punjab and Haryana High Court has made it clear that a husband may beg, borrow or steal for paying allowance to his wife and child, as his first and foremost duty was to maintain them (Source : <https://www.tribuneindia.com/news/archive/haryana/beg-borrow-or-steal-to-pay-wife-child-hc-679957>). and another court said do not use word BEG or Steal but order maintenance just because women is asking (Source: <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/chennai/avoid-beg-borrow-steal-adage-when-making-husbands-pay-maintenance-hc-to-family-court/articleshow/62515380.cms>). If women runaway with Lover, that's her choice, her body, she can have intimacy with anyone of her choice; but a man who does the same, society and judiciary term it as desertion or running away from responsibilities.

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OTHER INTIMIDATION TACTICS:

These include any words or actions the abusive partner uses to scare her partner. For example:

- ✓ Destroy property
- ✓ Throw or smash things
- ✓ Trash his clothes or other possessions
- ✓ Destroy keepsakes
- ✓ Break furniture or windows
- ✓ Threaten
- ✓ Threaten to harm or kill him
- ✓ Threaten to harm or kill herself or children, family, friends or pets
- ✓ Threaten to lie to authorities to put his child custody or legal status at risk
- ✓ Create a sense that punishment is just around the corner
- ✓ Stalk or harass
- ✓ Follow him after they have separated
- ✓ Show up at his workplace
- ✓ Go to his house and park outside
- ✓ Phone or send him mail repeatedly
- ✓ Phone or send mail to his family, friends or colleagues

Whether or not there are children involved, a man may stay in an abusive situation because:

- He feels afraid or guilty
- He feels he is financially insecure
- He feels a sense of obligation to his female partner
- He wants to honour his religious convictions or cultural expectations
- His partner reminds him of religious convictions or cultural expectations
- He still has hope for the relationship
- He feels ashamed to admit he is being abused

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A man with children may stay in the relationship because:

- He doesn't want to lose access to his children
 - He doesn't want to leave the children with his abusive partner
 - He may not trust the courts to handle child custody fairly
 - He doesn't want to be the one that "breaks up" the family
- ✓ Show up in party or function hosted by husband family with dirty or revealing cloths, create scene, flirt or act weird, shout, cry without reason, Abuse husband etc.

Society's attitudes can make it harder

Our society is beginning to recognize and study the abuse of men by their partners. Society's beliefs and attitudes about men have kept this kind of abuse hidden. Because of these beliefs, men who are abused by female partners may not admit it. They may not want to tell anyone. Additionally, sometimes police and other professionals may not take the abuse seriously.

As a result, a man in an abusive relationship may have some of these feelings:

- Afraid to tell anyone
- Depressed or humiliated
- Afraid he has failed as a lover and partner
- Guilty about leaving her or scared of coping alone
- Furious she could do or say the things she did
- Confused because sometimes she acts loving and kind
- Frustrated and sad because he has tried everything
- Afraid of continued violence or harassment if he leaves
- Panicked he may lose his male identity if people know what has been going on

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- Worried about his financial security
- Believes he deserved it

An abusive environment does harm children now and in their future.

Sometimes people abused by their partners think their children do not know about the abuse or that the abuse does not harm the children. But children are harmed, even if they are not directly abused.

Being exposed to anger and violence affects children's brain development.

- Brain scans show that children in abusive environments use much of their brain to watch out for danger. Less of their brain is available for healthy growth and development
- This affects their physical, emotional and mental development
- It affects their ability to form healthy relationships
- It affects them even when the children are not consciously aware of the abuse in their home

When a child is in a threatening environment over time, such as in a home where the adults are abusive, systems in the child's brain undergo changes. These changes result in emotional, behavioral, intellectual and physical symptoms. Children can show all the same signs of trauma as if they were abused themselves.

All children in a threatening environment are affected by fear. They might:

- Feel anxious or panicky
- Have an increased heart rate — babies in violent or angry homes have faster heart rates even in their sleep
- Be very watchful and attentive all the time, as though they are on “red alert”
- Because their brains are distracted by fear, they may:
- Find it hard to concentrate or pay attention

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- Have difficulty sleeping
- Have difficulty learning

Children in a threatening environment use different ways to cope.

Some children react by becoming more aggressive. They might:

- Be defiant
- Act impulsive
- Have angry outbursts
- Act bossy or pushy
- Bully or hurt others

Sometimes these loud children do not appear to be affected. They look like they feel confident and in charge. But their aggressive behaviors grow out of fear expressed outwardly as anger. Some children react by becoming quiet and withdrawn.

These children might:

- Try to stay safe by becoming “invisible”
- Go into their own fantasy world and tune out the world around them
- Be more obedient or passive than other children
- Be numb and disconnected from their own feelings
- Be detached from other people
- Have a hard time getting along with others
- Be depressed

Sometimes these quiet children, do not look like they are affected by what is going on around them. They do not appear to react. However, this “unaffected” appearance is a danger sign. In the face of fear and feeling helpless, they have disconnected from their environment.

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You may think that the abuse between adults in the home does not affect children, or that you can shield them from what is going on. That is not true. As long as children live in an abusive environment, the trauma will continue to affect their brains. They will not be able to heal.

Findings:

Men have suffered physical violence at the hands of an intimate partner or family member. In India after Domestic Violence Act, 2005 enacted, as it suffers from inherent flaws which tempt women to misuse their provisions and men to dread being prosecuted under the law without any rhyme or reason. The notable flaw in this law is that it lends itself to such easy misuse that women will find it hard to resist the temptation to teach a lesson to their male relatives and will file frivolous and false cases. One can be certain that there is something sinister about a law when it intimidates and instills fear in innocent people. When a person who has not committed any crime begins to fear punishment under the provisions of a law, it will certainly create panic amidst men. Now-a-days, filing cases under the Domestic Violence Act by women has become a common one. Therefore, a neutral and an unprejudiced law is needed to protect the genuine victims of domestic violence irrespective of their gender.

Domestic violence (also named domestic abuse, spousal abuse, intimate partner violence, battering, or family violence) is a pattern of behavior which involves violence or other abuse by one person against another in a domestic setting, such as in marriage or cohabitation. Intimate partner violence (IPV) is violence by a spouse or partner in an intimate relationship against the other spouse or partner. Domestic violence can take place in heterosexual and same-sex family relationships and can involve violence against children in the family. Domestic violence can take a number of forms, including physical, verbal, emotional, economic, cultural and

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sexual abuse, which can range from subtle, coercive forms to marital rape and to violent physical abuse such as female genital mutilation and acid throwing that result in disfigurement or death. Domestic murders include stoning, bride burning, honor killings, and dowry deaths.

Male victims of family violence and abuse - like women - often face many barriers to disclosing their abuse:

- They are likely to be told that there must be something they did to provoke the perpetrator's abuse
- They can suffer shame, embarrassment and the social stigma of not being able to protect themselves
- They can fear that if they disclose the abuse there will be nowhere for them and their children to escape to
- In cases of intimate partner violence, they can fear that if they disclose the abuse or end the relationship, their partner might become more abusive and/or take the children
- They can feel uncertain about where to seek help, or how to seek help
- Services are less likely to ask whether a man is a victim of family violence, and when they do ask, they are less likely to believe him (indeed many health departments have mandatory domestic violence screening for young women, but no such screening for young men). Male victims can be falsely arrested and removed from their homes because of the assumption that because they are male, they must be a perpetrator and not a victim. When this happens, children can be left unprotected from the perpetrator of the violence, leading many men to suffer the abuse in silence in an attempt to protect their children.

Because of these barriers, men are much less likely to under report being a victim of family violence compared to women.

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In India, family violence against men is almost legal as there is no provision in any law to protect a man, who faces violence from wife or other female family members. There are several cases where a husband has been battered, abused, tortured by wife in connivance with her own family. Many a times the violence is so brutal that the husband suffers extreme injuries, in some cases he is killed as well. This situation is mainly due to patriarchal thinking in the society, that men are stronger than women and they can defend themselves with physical force. It's high time India keeps pace with the rest of the world and makes the laws against domestic violence gender neutral.

Most abused men do not run away from their abusers and apply for divorce, because they are either afraid of losing access to their children or they are afraid of getting implicated in false cases of dowry harassment. They also dread huge financial losses and long drawn litigations in the process, given the insensitive and lackadaisical attitude of the Indian Judiciary, especially towards men.

In 2004, the National Family Health Survey (NFHS) has found that about 1.8% or an estimated 60 lakh women have perpetrated physical violence against husbands without any provocation. However, men are more likely to be threatened and attacked by male relatives of the wife than the wife herself. The strange aspect however is, men are not asked if they are victims of domestic violence in these surveys.

As per MyNation, When physical violence and threats against men by wife's relatives are taken into account, an estimated 3crore men are facing domestic violence in India.

As there is a lot of social stigma towards men abused by women, most of the male victims do not come out in open and do not share their ordeal with family, friends or colleagues. Male victims of domestic violence are ridiculed and considered as unmanly. Such thinking is chauvinistic and is harmful.

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Violence on men can range from anything like - physical violence including slapping, pushing, hitting by wife, her parents and her relatives; emotional violence with wife threatening suicide to intimidate and control the husband; verbal abuse if husband remains in contact with his parents or comes home late from work; throwing objects like utensils, mobile phones and crockery at the husband; sexual abuse if husband denies sex to mental abuse by constant threats of implicating the husband and his family under false case of dowry and domestic violence.

Today, many women have serious anger management issues. They also seem to bring the stress of the workplace to the home. This is one of the main reasons of domestic violence against men. The other reasons include intolerance and anger at non-fulfillment of expectations.

Sometimes, inability of husband to meet monetary demands of wife also leads to abuse and violence

Times are changing and there are many men whose wives are more educated than their husbands and earn more. However, the burden of running the house still rests on the man owing to 16th century patriarchal beliefs and this paves the path for abuse of men. Such a law could allow such husbands to seek maintenance from an abusive wife and lead a dignified life free from abuse.

Male victims of family violence go through low self-esteem and their performance at workplace suffers. Thousands of such men are approaching psychiatrists, who are not of much help, when a law to provide protection to men and restrain the women does not exist.

Most parents of women blame the son-in-law for the breakdown of the marriage, without accepting that their daughter is abusive, or she has serious anger management issues. They somehow think their daughter can never be wrong and expect the son-in-law to tolerate her. They get violent at son-in-law to teach him a

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lesson or seek revenge. Police rarely accepts any complaints filed by husband about the violence he is suffering, claiming that this is a family issue. They also refuse to provide any protection to the man.

The patriarchal thinking that “Mardko Dard nahi hota” (Men do not feel pain) eulogizes and patronizes emotional castration of boys from a very young age which teaches them to tolerate abuse and feel glorified about making sacrifices. Owing to this social conditioning, a vast majority of victimized men wear a plastic smile and hide their scars and suffer in solitude.

The survey conducted by National Family Health Survey which throws light on unprovoked violence against men by women is evidence in the face. Notwithstanding the fact that double the numbers of men commit suicide compared to women, it should not be a surprise to ask for a law to protect men as such a law for women already exists. In fact, it would be preposterous in this age of gender equality, not to have such a law. Such a law to protect men from domestic violence would act occurs to millions of those men who feel victimized and left out.

It would also provide them with a legal platform to come forward and share their pain and get some semblance of relief.

These days MEN are becoming victims of domestic violence, abuse against men in the home is on the rise. When we talk about Gender Equality, we shall not forget our age-old culture. When we talk about Women Empowerment, need not to think about disempowerment of men. When we talk about Justice for all, need not to forget that men are a part of all". Indian Men Suicide is rising after marriage, rising and rising anyone can check Crime Bureau Report of India for more detail.

Men can be reluctant to say that they are victims, and they worry that they won't be believed. Constitution of India says “All people of India shall be guaranteed and

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secured social, economic and political justice; equality of status and opportunities before law; and fundamental freedom.” then

WHY Indian men have no Equality in Laws?

WHY Indian Domestic Laws are biased towards men?

WHY It takes 7 Years to get Divorce to men and only 6 months to Indian women?

WHY Indian Fathers are denied to Child Custody, Even Mother is criminal?

WHY Indian men have no Protection Laws?

WHY Men do not get Reservations too?

When there is no law / Judiciary support, how can a man lead normal happy life... All these facts are a clear indication that Indian husbands are harassed more than Indian women, at home and judicially

“Domestic violence against men in India is not recognized by the law. The general perception is that men cannot be victims of violence. This helps women get away scot-free,” and the judiciary almost always favors the woman. “Domestic violence cases are supposed to be resolved in six months, but this never happens. Once a case is filed, the husband has to attend every hearing — which takes place once every 10 days — otherwise he is viewed as the wrongdoer in the court’s eye. Mind you, there are no questions raised if the woman doesn’t attend hearings.”

Like women, men also find it hard to get out of abusive relationships, but situation is worse for men, as they not only fear being away from their children but are also worried about a false dowry case being filed against them. Men who are accused of domestic violence get marginalized by society and even friends and family turn their backs on them, for men, it is huge emotional battle, one which proved to be

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too much for a man. If any Man approaches the police after he was assaulted by his wife, and the cops not only ridicule him, sometimes Police even call his wife and ask her to file a case against him. So as to force him to take his own life, when there are no options left for him.

NCRB STATISTICS

498A

Year	Case Registered	Total PERSONS Arrested	Persons Acquitted (cases)	Conviction Rate
2011	99135	180701	83580	20.6
2012	106527	197762	92867	15.0
2013	118866	222091	97622	15.2
2014	122877	225648	94765	14.0
2015	113403	187067	88203	15.7
2016	110378	198851	82075	10.10
2017	104551	135340	84679	12.19
2018	103272	110789	70171	09.93

DVA

Year	Case Registered	Total Arrest	acquitted	Conviction Rate
2011	107753	205279	94757	22.8
2012	114760	222180	103113	16.7
2013	126949	245955	108003	16.7
2014	135492	255107	104805	15.7
2015	125558	213835	98899	17.7
2016	9683		18025	
2017	86001			
2018	89097			

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Why men suffer in silence

Protect children: Just like women, men worry that leaving their spouses will harm their children or prevent them from having access to them. Obtaining custody of children is always challenging for fathers, as is the prospect of raising them alone.

Feel ashamed: Many men feel ashamed at being beaten by a woman or feel that they have failed in their role as a protector and provider for the family.

Fear of false cases: The biggest fear in Indian men is being slapped with a dowry harassment case. Not only is it hard to shake off the social stigma that comes with being charged with such an act, but the cases also tend to drag on for years and are almost always in the woman's favor.

Parental pressure: Even today, most men continue to live with their parents even after getting married. When differences arise, parents generally step in and can sometimes make matters worse with their own demands.

Denial: Just as with female domestic violence victims, denying that there is a problem only prolongs the abuse. Men believe that they can help or change their abuser, but change can only happen once the abuser takes full responsibility for her behavior and seeks professional treatment.

Emotional abuse: Emotional abuse of men is the same as emotional abuse of women: it is act including verbal assault, that make a person feel less self-worth or dignity. Emotional abuse of men makes them feel like less of a person.

Male victims of emotional abuse may experience partners that:

- Yell and scream
- Threaten them and try to induce fear

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- Insult and demean them; tell them they are not worth the trouble
- Socially isolate them
- Lie or withhold information
- Treat them like a child or servant
- Control all the finances

Some believe that men are more sensitive to emotional abuse than woman and can "brush off" physical abuse more easily. Male victims of emotional abuse who are called a "coward," "impotent," or a "failure," maybe more affected by these remarks than their female counterparts.

Controlling and emotionally abusive behaviors elicited by women may include:

- Falsely accusing or threatening to accuse a man of assault on them or their children
- Threatening to take away custody of the children
- Threatening to kill themselves or others
- Making the man feel like "he's crazy"
- Minimizing the abuse; blaming the victim of the abuse
- Playing mind games
- Making the man feel guilty
- Falsely obtaining a restraining order
- Withholding affection
- Stalking

Like women, many men stay in emotionally abusive relationships. This can be for many reasons but certainly in part due to the toll that emotional abuse can take on a man's self-worth. He may not believe he is worthy enough to leave the relationship or he may believe he deserves the emotional abuse.

Men may also stay in emotionally abusive relationships because:

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- Of threats made by their abuser
- To protect the children
- They feel dependent on the abuser

Reproductive rights of man

"Reproductive rights" are the rights of individuals to decide whether to reproduce and have reproductive health. This may include an individual's right to plan a family, terminate a pregnancy, use contraceptives, learn about sex education in public schools, and gain access to reproductive health services.

Historically, in India people do not publicly discuss about the reproductive rights due to the moral, ethical, and religious undertones of birth control, abortion, and family planning. Today, the subject of reproductive rights continues to be an emotionally and politically charged issue, especially in light of new technologies and recent laws.

The Indian Constitution does not explicitly mention a right to reproduce, however, the Supreme Court has recognized it as a personal right that is deemed "fundamental".

Do Men Have Reproductive Rights?

While reproductive rights have been legally recognized as a woman's right - especially in matters involving abortion, adoption, and procreation - men's reproductive rights have been less certain.

Constitutionally, laws must only guarantee that men and women are treated the same if they are "similarly situated" - which they are not in matters of reproduction.

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Abortion is the single most controversial issue involving Reproductive Rights. The issue turns on whether a woman should have the "right" to terminate a pregnancy that would amount to a living human being if remained untouched without her partner consent.

Indian court decided that the abortion falls within a person's constitutional right to privacy, believing the choice to terminate an "unborn fetus" lies with the individual and her doctor. Hence, a man does not have rights to decide whether his wife can abort a child or not.

The World Health Organization defines reproductive rights as “rest[ing] on the recognition of the basic right of all couples and individuals to decide freely and responsibly the number, spacing, and timing of their children and to have the information and means to do so, and the right to attain the highest standard of sexual and reproductive health. They also include the right of all to make decisions concerning reproduction free of discrimination, coercion, and violence.

Women are also under no legal requirement to identify the father of their child and if the father is not listed on the birth certificate, he has no legal rights at all. Certainly, men can pursue legal rights by establishing paternity, but it is up to men to enforce their rights. Women can, and do, surrender infants for adoption without notifying or identifying the father of the child. These are very high risk adoptions for the adopting couple, because there is always a chance the father will appear and attempt to assert his rights, but the fact remains that women can, once again, relieve themselves of all social, legal, financial and moral responsibility for a child they do not want.

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The WHO says reproductive rights require that no person be coerced into parenthood, meaning that men do not have reproductive rights, as long as that coercion exists.

Worst is not over for Indian single man:

Adoption: Single women and men are allowed to adopt but single men can only adopt boys. Adoption agencies harbor biases against single people specially for man. In 2015, the Ministry of Women and Child Development issued the Central Adoption Resource Agency (CARA) Guideline which permits a single woman to adopt a kid of any gender. The Juvenile Justice Act does not lawfully prescribe a single male to adopt a female child. Single men and live-in couples will soon not be able to adopt in India.

The Ministry of Women and Child Development is set to notify a new set of guidelines for adoption, which are far stricter about couples who are not married, and single men.

They also specify the age at which married couples and single women can adopt.

Surrogacy: In August 2016, the Union Cabinet passed a bill banning single men, women, and gay couples from opting for surrogacy. As per the new bill, surrogacy for foreigners and persons of Indian origin is also banned in the country. Commercial surrogacy (paying someone to be a surrogate) is prohibited; only blood relatives between the age of 25 to 35 years can now become a surrogate. Also, the woman opting to become a surrogate mother should be married and with a child of her own.

The Surrogacy (Regulation) Bill, 2019: The surrogacy bill prevents single parents, same-sex couples, divorced or widowed persons, transgender persons, live-in partners and foreign nationals from using a surrogate mother.

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MEDIA REFERENCE: These are media coverage of men Murdered in the hands of their wives. This is just a tip of the iceberg as very few news media dare to publish, there are 100 times more such cases which are not covered or termed as suicide/accidental deaths or if women kill that termed as she killed in her defence.

MyNation dare to challenge any Women organization, if they can produce such murder reports committed by men and killed their wives.

These are news Links between Jan 2020 to May 2020.

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CONCLUSION: As long as Indian government is under control of Feminists lobby, there will be no law for men, nor will they get any relief. It is assumed men are always the abuser and women are always the victim this common misconception should change but that's impossible dream as long as there is no option for men to complain/report of their domestic abuse.

RECOMMENDATION: NEED OF MINISTRY FOR MEN AND GENDER-NEUTRAL LAWS.

TESTIMONIALS: (In victims own words – no any change or even spell check)

1). **Dr. Bharat Bhushan :** Emotional violence, NOT an uncommon Story :

My dentist wife left no stone unturned to harass me mentally everyday when she compared my house to her native and went on to say that she was raised as princess by her parents where her every demand was met, never did household works and preferred to keep her earnings to herself without contributing anything to the family. She was often reluctant to mingle with my parents & family and refused to stay in my native with my parents but wanted every financial decision of the family to be taken under her behest. Me and my parents were ridiculed for no reason whenever her lavish demands were not met. We failed to acknowledge her attitude as she was new to our place and we felt that it was just a casual misunderstanding between the newly married couple.

Further, her verbal abuse, constant criticism, intimidation, refusing to listen, refusing to communicate, blaming, shaming, refusal to ever be pleased and constant interference from her family members left our whole family in pain. This went on for more than a year and whole family was literally broken. Finally, my

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wife left me without any reason, filed false cases of domestic violence on my family and now demanding money to withdraw cases. The emotional violence she has committed on me in particular and my family as a whole has left us in cross roads.

I was surprised to get support from my neighborhood as they were aware of abusive and rude nature of my wife but police refused to take any action as the law has tied their hands to act against abusive women even though she is a culprit. Furthermore, being an well qualified dentist, she is demanding maintenance from me and it was very surprising that she hid her qualification details from court of law under the guidance of her lawyer brother. Knowingly or unknowingly some lawyers and police are often encouraging the emotional violence in the form of fake cases to extort money like this as they are very well aware of lack of law to punish false accuser.

In this context, it is very much needed to address the issue of all forms of domestic violence on men who are suffering due to lack of law on domestic violence on men by the spouse and punishment to false accusers.

2). **Vardharajan A** : Fake case which runs for years, all our hard earned money is going into the pockets of lawyer's and government bodies who least bother to protect us. Each cases which is not closed with mutual consent minimum runs for 5 years.

No one can compensate the father's pain during this journey. Our health, time, hard earned money and parents happiness is completely ruined by this feminist mafia.

Above all our children's are forced to get alienated from their beloved ones which put their future in deep trouble.

3). **Ankit Kulshrestha** : While victims of domestic violence men too face abuse in their house however the law doesn't treat them as victims, when men try to register

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their complaint or narrate problem or harassment within marriage to police station no one listen to them.

Sometime he continue to stay in violent relationship due to many reasons like love towards children, fear of societal blame but it is equally important to understand consequence of such act on his health. In most of the cases against male his wife use more mental verbal emotional violence rather than physical

4). **Vivek Kumar** : On upcoming generation citing scar on young minds when their mothers, grandparents live in the terror of such litigations. Also, about how state doesn't want to discuss or take steps towards equality and follows bad prudence from other countries like divorce laws in property. One side it takes steps like decriminalizing adultery and then other side doesn't put a cap on maintenance for short-lived marriages and extorts husbands for lifetime.

5). **Vikrant Banode** : Fed up of wife's emotional, mental and financial harassment, husband thinks of committing suicide; saved by his family and friends, files a divorce. Wife and in-laws in with huge financial approaches supreme court and get the case transferred to another State.

Wife later files a fake Domestic Violence case along with a false rent agreement. At the time of her submission of evidence and cross examination in both cases, wife and in-laws heads towards compromise of issues.

After joining back to matrimonial life, wife starts the same thing. She makes a false complaint to human rights and Police.

So there seems no change in women and all our hard earned money is going into the pockets of lawyer's and government bodies who least bother to protect us. Our health, time, hard earned money and family happiness get completely ruined. Children are getting alienated.

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This is a gross misuse of laws and a personality disorder that seems growing day by day and our government rather to dilute the issues are making more and more stricter, gender biased laws, resulting in family breakages.

6). **Sharan Shetty** : Most of these gender biased marital cases are only done to terrorise men and their family so u bow down to the demands ,love was never there and no questions about it the only person to blame for the whole scenario is a fake women (wife/ gf) who have made all the women even the real ones suffer, Now why is a general educated middle class man targeted it's just because he has lot to lose(career,time,money and Respect) not to forget the agony of his family which consists of women too, Transparency accountability, justice are not common daily words but I have seen none of them in the police and then in judiciary , when just with a blink of eye you can separate the truth from the rest but still you are just provided dates which just add salts to your wounds. I am a professional engineer travelled and worked around the world and now I am trapped in a mythical cage with nil presence in modern world or maybe some greed of my ancestors were in they did not act quickly to abolish the root cause this punishment is just because I did not settle the matter with all the concerned parties, The key everybody suggest for this door is how much amount you can shelve, the door will open quicker only when your key is bigger, I choose to fight my way through so I can feel better.

7). **Shriram Yadav** : Soon after few days of marriage, wife started creating issues of trifle things. Wife bid husband for abortion; when made understand, exclaimed and refused by husband, wife along her parents tried to create a scene and deserted the husband. Even then the husband carried out his duty and tried fie reconciliation, but in vein. Wife tried to humiliate and defame husband in the society.

These are modern women and their ego of being in power, as the Gender biased laws are in their favor. They enter and keep on ruining a man's life and Indian government supports them.

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8). **Amit Nishania** : After 18mnths of marriage my wife left home and after many request from my side I failed to make her stay together. Later they wanted divorce for no reason and demanded an hefty amount with share in my father's property. I accepted the divorce call but was not willing to give anything as she failed to state any reason for divorce. Later almost after 1 year of separation they filed FIR against me and my family with a DV case in addition, demanding 10lac as compensation and 20k pm as maintenance. With the help of group and continuous study of law and case study I was able to make her understand by my reply against petition that she will gain nothing. They approached many times for mutual divorce but after 1 year of case filed I accepted their proposal and choose to move ahead in life. Within 18 months of case filed I am free from my cruel wife. But I know I need to fight against this cruel and biased law, so will continue my fight.

9). **Aman Kumar** : Due to a near fatal bike accident in 2003, I am partially paralysed (60%) since 17-years and at present working with bank since 2014.

Got married in June 2016 .

Initially She agreed to live with me and mine aged parents, however, soon within 20 days of marriage, she left her matrimonial home.

Together we have a 3 yrs old baby girl

Our relationship was on and off , she returned again in September 2017 after daughter's birth.

She left home once again in March 2018 and filed a case of dowry harassment and domestic violence against me & my complete family.

Her main demand was that I separates from my mother, moves into a separate home and also She must get a share in my mother's property. I was physically assaulted too.

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I have to fight up to Supreme court, finally divorce was granted and the custody of the daughter remained with wife with visitation rights, but she never honored this

10). **Ramesh Thatiseti** : An arranged Marriage where you say YES in few days of first meeting and keep taking it further in hope of better days, even though u get to know you are cheated in few weeks.

They deceived us by showing as a respectable family. There is no dowry and is even admitted by them in first complaint.

They are dominating every decision even before marriage and we never thought it is an issue.

She always finds fault in everything. She literally don't know how to treat any person.

Forget about she doing even a bit of house hold works, it would be a great day if she did not find any fault in my cooking, cleaning, serving her and her needs of shopping, roaming outside and what not.

And soon, it turned out to be shouting, warning and criminal intimidations on me and family if her expectations are not met.

They frequently intimidated saying like they are known Rowdy Sheeters and can knock off anyone.

No one could help me, instead warned to be careful with them as they are dangerous rowdies.

I tried to get help from Courts but for them mine is an interesting story and only suggestion is to pay them and get rid of them.

I am not allowed to meet my son, even on his first birthday they allowed just 10 minutes to be with him and then took him away.

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They filed multiple cases, corrupted police and put absolutely fake allegations.

Dragged all my family into cases, even when they have not met her for years.

DV is a very small word for the pain, I am going through. I am directly warned to be killed.

Her father is a criminal, now that they decided to break the marriage, they want to go extreme ways.

Unfortunately, many complaints on them have fallen to deaf ears. I get the complaint copy stamped and all that is it.

NO LAW for MEN. I can't fight those criminals. They corrupted every department and section.

11). **Niraj Upadhyay** : The women in India can invoke and abuse the one sided legal provisions in the name of domestic violence or 498A or crpc 125 and ask for huge compensation. No matter married for 3 month or 3 years or 30 years..They control and brainwash the kids while the breadwinner is slogging in office for livelihood. Only rights and no obligations ...It is a loose situation for men emotionally, physically and financially. Worst is when you are treated as ATM machine for your kids being biological father means nothing..Aakhir Mard Ko Dard nahi hota is the spirit in which Indian Laws operate. She can destroy his life, family and everything at any point just at the drop of hat. I am facing an extortion game planned by my wife and her parents using my 12 year kid as blackmailing tool to fund her luxurious desires and old age pension account for her cunning parents. Lost my mother and physically ailing father with brain stroke and myself suffering a stroke. Denial of access to child till Ransom is paid..Law book says something but legal system interprets it feminist way..But wait I am there to take up the challenge and it is a fight for existence as have nothing to lose now..Beware of me.

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12). **Sandeep kumar nath** : My marriage was done in 2010. After the 4th day of marriage my wife started make quarrel in home and stated to humiliate my parents and other family member . She don't try to touch home work and always stay in her room . She always used to harassed us and tried to torture on the name of fake case . She always warned us either my father's transfer property on her name or she will file fake case on our family bcoz her uncle is in police . In February 2011 a girl baby born and we take care for her as per we can but she never changed her behave.

Then my father disowned me and arrange a rental accommodation for me and my wife .

On rental accommodation she lives near about 11 month and she always started quarrel in rental home also .

Once day in January 2013 when I went to shop , I got a call from police and they tell me your wife give a complaint and now you come to police station. When I went there they handcuffed me on the name of fake harassment . Then she made a fake agreement there that she didn't want to pursue complaint.

After that she made 3 to 4 bogus complaint but never came back .

after many request from my side I failed to make her stay together. Then she filed fake 498a , domestic violence and other cases .

After 4 yrs of mentally harassment to me and my family the honorable court dismissed her petition and clearly write in his judgment that the case filed by the wife is clearly a vase to harassed in-laws and relative .

Court clearly says it is the misuse of the law and process . But I know I need to fight against this cruel and biased law, so will continue my fight.

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13). **Prasad Challapalli** : she left my house with in 16days in between she stay in my home only 6 days and demanding 30lakhs, she gave nothing and Marriage also performed by us, after one year she filed false 498A package on 12 of my family and relatives now I am fighting for divorce without any alimony

14). **Rajendra Sharma** : I was working in a reputed MNC. Got married in year 2013. Marriage was done without any dowry item exchange. However my family gifted lot of jewellery to my wife. Just after few days of marriage we get to know she had major medical condition and she is a psychic girl. Her treatment was done at various hospital prior to marriage, she came to my house with full of medicines. She was unfit for the marriage, she was unable to handle household, unable to produce child. All these things were hid to us by her and her family. When I and my family get to know it she and her parents started threatening us of killing and fake cases. Soon she left my house on her own. She started abusing and blackmailing me and my family on phone. Soon she gave complain for dowry harassment at her hometown. Police started harassing us on the name of settlement. Soon fake dowry case was filed on me and my innocent family.

We hired a lawyer, but these lawyers are big dacoits, for any such matrimonial issue lawyer are big villain. Such girls, police, lawyers, court are blood sucker of innocent men.

As men has no law to save himself, I was also helpless. I and my family went to depression, money problem, emotional problem.

She is PhD still she is unable to maintain herself, however she was earning before marriage.

On the name of taking cases back she is asking 50 lacs as alimony.

Such harassment can only be stopped when all the laws will be made gender neutral and there is strict punishment for fake cases. Accountability of judges and

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police is also important, if they files fake cases and run them in court then they should also be sent to jail. By shutting down all the women NGO and their loot, they motivate women to break their marriage. No lawyer should be allowed during matrimonial case. Alimony should be illegal as dowry. Social boycott of such family who files fake cases.

15). **Ramu G** : Even though my wife and her family knew that she is suffering from Epilepsy disease and other medical issues, they concealed it intentionally before our marriage. When I came to know about her Epilepsy disease just 2 weeks after our marriage, My parents then advised that as the marriage is already completed, it was our responsibility to take care of her and provide her further medical treatment. My wife frequently had epileptic attacks approx every 1 or 2 months and I used to take her to that same doctor, who was treating her initially. While Me and my family always treated my wife with due care and provided her complete medical care due to her medical condition, my wife started ill-treating my Parents and other family members when they visited us. I have silently observed all her ill and cruel behavior towards me and my family right since our marriage and one day when I questioned her the same, she was very rude with me and even threatened me that she will reach Police authorities with complaints. Citing health reasons, she left my home within 6 months of our marriage and lodged a false dowry complaint on me and my entire family who were living separately. My wife started demanding a huge amount of Rs 30 Lakhs in the name of settlement with an intention to extort money from me. Due to these false cases, my and our family members are subjected to intolerable mental agony, financial burden and stress driving entire family into depression and health issues. Me and my family became a scapegoat for NO FAULT OF US. As I showed my helplessness to pay that huge amount, Police have registered the FIR and even opened a Charge Sheet on my entire family without even any verifications and I'm currently attending court with a hope that I would get justice.

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16). **Abhishek Sharma** : Within first 15 days of my marriage, my wife separated us from my parents by regular quarrelling with us ,refusing to do any work, spreading lies in my ears against my parents, using foul language against me and my parents, calling her divorced mother/ relatives to accompany her to quarrel and do as she says or threaten us that they will injure us and separate us from my parents. After separation from my parents she along with her mother and relatives harassed me by quarrelling with me every day in groups that I bring money, FD and part of my property from my parents and they will help me by hook or crook. She Kept all her and mine things and threw me out of the house in association with her mother. it seemed like she was very well prepared by her divorced mother. My parents got us a rented furnished accommodation where she first refused to stay with me, then came only to quarrel with me daily, create situations for fight, threatening me for calling police to make me fear her by saying u r harassing me, beating me, not letting me sleep by disturbing me , hiding my things like car keys, spec, phone etc, coming to my office and start creating situations by crying etc. Disturbing me and colleagues. Tried harassing me in every possible way. left house at times for hours without telling, throwing kitchen items on floor, sent false complaints to my office.

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